
Mass of a photon

Author:

Andreas STOKKELAND

Email:

s.andreas.m.dealings@icloud.com

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As my understanding of $E = mc^2$ is that most energies can be translated into a mass according to the formula, this could be done with the energy of a photon. Thus you would get the following:

$$hf = mc^2 \iff m = \frac{h}{c^2}f . \quad (1)$$

Where m is the mass of a photon, f is the frequency of a photon, c is the speed of light, and h is the Planck's constant. With $c = f\lambda$, where λ is the wavelength of light, you can rewrite Eq.(1) as follows.

$$m = \frac{h}{c^2} \frac{c}{\lambda} = \frac{h}{c\lambda} \iff \lambda = \frac{h}{cm} . \quad (2)$$

We can here see that this is basically a rediscovery of the de Broglie wavelength, but for the special case where $v = c$.

This property of light, being that it has mass, could explain the dark mass that we see. This I would say is an improvement on what is found in [1].

References

- [1] Alain Haraux. "On relativistic kinetic energy and the mass of photons." In: *arXiv* (). DOI: <https://arxiv.org/html/2312.11065v1/>.